

Relationship Between Total Protein and Energy Consumption and Hemoglobin Levels in Adolescents with High Body Mass Index

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Abstract

Introduction. Children and teenagers who are at risk of being overweight are twice as likely to experience iron deficiency, which can cause anemia. This study aimed to discuss the correlation between total protein and energy intake and hemoglobin levels in obese adolescents who were medical students. **Materials and methods.** This study employed a cross-sectional analytical method. Subject selection began by measuring body weight and height to determine BMI according to the selection category. Subsequently, a 24-hour recall interview was conducted to assess energy and protein intake on two weekdays and one weekend. To assess hemoglobin levels and red blood cell indices, blood samples were collected by the Clinical Pathology Laboratory at Hasan Sadikin Hospital, Bandung. **Results.** A total of 13 samples aged 18-19 years who met the selection criteria had a protein intake of 68.79 g/day (SD 22.80 g/day), total energy intake of 1822.31 kcal/day (SD 441.34 kcal/day) and hemoglobin 15.4 g/dL (10.3-16.4 g/dL). Spearman's rho test showed a correlation of protein intake with hemoglobin levels $r = 0.489$, $p > 0.05$ and a correlation of total energy intake with hemoglobin levels $r = 0.452$, $p > 0.05$. **Conclusion.** There was no correlation between total protein and energy intake and hemoglobin levels in late-age adolescents who were obese at the Faculty of Medicine, Padjadjaran University, a class of 2016.

Introduction

The occurrence of overnutrition and undernutrition is the result of an imbalance between energy intake and the energy intake required by the body [1]. Socio-economic factors, food consumption patterns, physical activity patterns, and lifestyle have a strong influence on the increase in the prevalence of overnutrition [2]. Adolescents are experiencing a phase of rapid growth, so relatively large amounts of nutrients are required [3]. Irregular eating habits such as eating snacks, consuming lots of fast food or instant food, consuming less vegetables and fruit, or reducing carbohydrate intake such as rice, often occur in adolescents in various countries. This causes adolescents to experience more nutritional problems [3].

According to the Basic Health Research (Riskesdas), the incidence of obesity in 2013 was 32.9% for women in their late teens (>18 years) and 19.7 % % for men in their late teens (>18 years). This result has increased threefold compared to 2007 [4]. On a world scale, obesity has become a colossal epidemic and causes serious concern in the field of public health and causes 2.6 million deaths worldwide each year [5].

A high intake of macronutrients, such as carbohydrates and fats, is a common problem in nutritional status. Carbohydrates, proteins, and fat influence the incidence of obesity (overnutrition) through the effects of food intake, digestion, absorption of nutrients, and metabolism in the body. Obesity can also be caused by a less active lifestyle (sedentary lifestyle). This lifestyle has been commonly observed in the last few decades

More Information

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and is characterized by reduced physical activity [6]. Excessive energy intake from foods that are not balanced with sufficient nutritional activity increases the risk of obesity [7].

Anemia is a condition in which the number of red blood cells or the capacity to carry oxygen is insufficient according to the body’s physiological needs, and varies depending on age, sex, area of residence, smoking habits, or pregnancy status [8,9]. According to data from Riskesdas in 2013, the prevalence of anemia in Indonesia was 21.7% with anemia sufferers aged 5-14 years amounting to 26.4% and 18.4% of sufferers aged 15-24 years [10]. A study shows that iron deficiency anemia is generally high in women aged 18-24 years old [11].

In general, the high prevalence of anemia is caused by iron deficiency, but several other factors, such as vitamin A, vitamin C, folic acid, riboflavin, and vitamin B12 also have an influence [12]. Protein intake in the body helps in the absorption of iron; therefore, proteins collaborate with protein chains to transport electrons, which play a role in energy metabolism [13]. Good protein intake causes good body growth and can influence optimum hemoglobin production [14]

Based on research by the American Academy of Pediatrics, children and adolescents who are at risk of being overweight are twice as likely to experience iron deficiency, which can cause anemia (Alshwaiyat et al., 2021). New evidence suggests that the mechanism of anemia and overweight is a decrease in iron absorption or use due to inflammation caused by obesity (obesity-related inflammation). Serum hepcidin peptide levels increase during obesity and affect iron concentration [15].

Many studies have examined the relationship between energy intake and nutritional status of adolescents or the relationship between nutritional status and the incidence of anemia; however, little research has been conducted on total protein and energy intake and the incidence of anemia in obese and overweight adolescents. Therefore, researchers are interested in investigating the features of anemia, total protein, and energy intake in overweight and obese adolescents.

Methods

This study is correlative analytical research with a cross-sectional approach. The research data were primary data in the form of measurements of protein intake, total energy, hemoglobin levels, and red blood cell index in obese first-year students of the Faculty of Medicine, Padjadjaran University class of 2016. This study was conducted from April to May 2017.

There were 13 subjects who took part in this research. The inclusion criteria in this study were students from the 2016 Faculty of Medicine, Padjadjaran University, aged 17-19 years and obese based on the WHO growth reference of 5-19 years, namely greater than two

standard deviations above the median or according to the obesity category according to the WHO Asia Pacific. 15 Age determination was determined based on the last birthday. The exclusion criteria were students who were unwilling to participate in the research and were not present when data were collected.

Subject selection begins with measuring body weight and height to determine BMI according to the selection category. Subsequently, a 24-hour recall interview was conducted to assess energy and protein intake. 24-hour recall interviews were conducted 2 times to obtain food data on two weekdays and on one weekend. To equalize the weight of food ingredients, a food weigher is used, and the Food Ingredient Exchange List from the Hasan Sadikin Hospital Bandung Nutrition Installation, which is used in household measurements in grams, is used. After obtaining the weight of the food in grams, the total protein and energy contents were calculated using the Nutrisurvey application in accordance with the nutritional calculations of the FAO Indonesian Food Database. The subjects’ total protein and total energy intakes per day were compared with the Nutritional Adequacy Table and placed into the category of insufficient or excessive intake.

Blood sampling to assess hemoglobin levels and red blood cell index was performed by the Clinical Pathology Laboratory Installation at Hasan Sadikin Hospital, Bandung. Hemoglobin levels were classified as normal, mild anemia, moderate anemia, or severe anemia. For the red blood cell index results were normochromic normocytic, normochromic macrocytic, or hypochromic microcytic.

The data obtained were descriptively and analytically analyzed. Descriptive data are presented in tables to describe their characteristics. Analytical data were analyzed using statistical correlation tests. Data analysis was performed using Microsoft Excel and the Statistical Program for Social Science (SPSS).

Result

Table 1 presents the sample characteristics of the study. The sample consisted of eight men and five women, with four aged 18 years, eight aged 19 years, and one aged 20 years. The age composition based on sex was four men aged 18 years and four men aged 19 years, while for women aged 19 years, there were four people and one person aged 20 years.

Table 1: Subject Characteristics

Characteristics	Gender		Total
	Male	Female	
Age			
18	4	-	4
19	4	5	9
Total	8	5	13

Table 2 shows protein intake. The category of protein adequacy level is classified into severe deficit, namely <70% RDA, moderate deficit 70-79% RDA, mild deficit 80-89% RDA, normal 90-119% RDA and more ≥120% RDA.19 In this study there were five people and eight people had good protein intake. The results of analysis using Shapiro-Wilk showed that protein intake data had a normal distribution with a mean of 68.79 g/day (SD 22.80 g/day).

Table 2: Protein Intake Levels

Variable	Total
Severe deficiency	2
Moderate deficiency	2
Mild deficiency	-
Normal	3
Excess	6
Total	13

Table 3 lists the total energy intakes of the samples. The category of energy adequacy level is classified into severe deficit, namely <70% RDA, moderate deficit 70-79% RDA, mild deficit 80-89% RDA, normal 90-119% RDA and more ≥120% RDA.19 The entire sample of thirteen people had a total energy intake level of less. The results of analysis using Shapiro-Wilk showed that protein intake data had a normal distribution with a mean of 1822.31 kcal/day (SD 441.34 kcal/day).

Table 3: Total Energy Intake Level

Variable	Total
Severe deficiency	6
Moderate deficiency	2
Mild deficiency	2
Normal	3
Excessive	-
Total	13

Table 4 shows the hemoglobin levels in this study, 12 people had normal hemoglobin levels and one person had low hemoglobin levels in the category of moderate anemia. The results of analysis using Shapiro-Wilk showed that the hemoglobin level data had an abnormal distribution. The mean hemoglobin level of the samples was 15.4 g/dL (10.3-16.4 g/dL)

Table 4: Hemoglobin Level

Variable	Jumlah
Normal	12
Mild anemia	-
Moderate anemis	1
Severe anemia	-
Total	13

Table 5 shows a picture of the red blood cell index of samples with normal hemoglobin levels from 12 people, five of whom were normochromic normocytic, one was hypochromic macrocytic, and six were hypochromic normocytic. There was one person in the sample who had anemia, the type of anemia was microcytic hypochromic anemia.

Table 5: Red Blood Cell Index

Variables	Total
Normocytic normochrome	5
Normocytic hypochrome	6
Macrocytic hypochrome	1
Macrocytic hypochrome	1
Total	13

Correlation analysis of protein intake and hemoglobin levels using Spearman's rho showed no significant correlation (r = 0.489, p = 0.90), and no correlation was found between energy intake and hemoglobin levels (r = 0.452, p = 0.121).

Table 6: Correlation Iron Intake and Hemoglobin Level

Variable	Hemoglobin level	
	r	P
Protein intake	0.489	0.90
Total energy intake	0.452	0.121

Note: r, correlation coefficient; p, significancy

Discussion

One in 13 obese teenagers in this study had low hemoglobin levels, which fell into the category of moderate microcytic hypochromic anemia, and the sample was female. This is in accordance with the theory that men are less at risk of anemia than women, because female adolescents experience iron losses of approximately 0.8 mg/day.

Based on the factors causing obesity, it is known that one of the main causes of obesity is characterized by reduced physical activity [16]. In this study, it was found that ten of 13 samples consumed < 70% of the recommended total energy intake. In this study, no samples were found to have excessive energy consumption, but one sample had anemia. This is contrary to Permaesih's research theory, that teenagers who consume >70% more energy have a higher risk of anemia than normal conditions [16]

A total of six samples experienced excess protein intake, which is in accordance with theory, in obese adolescents there is an increase in macronutrient intake including protein which influences the incidence of obesity (overnutrition) through the effects of food intake, digestion, absorption of nutrient intake, and metabolism in the body [17]. This affects iron

concentration and increases the risk of anemia [17]. However, this study does not match the theory because only one of the 13 people in the sample experienced anemia. This is in accordance with previous research that there is no significant relationship between protein intake and anemia [18].

In this study, there was no correlation between total protein, energy intake, and hemoglobin levels in obese adolescents. It is possible that the body can still compensate for the lack of protein intake in obese adolescents without affecting the structure of hemoglobin or disrupting absorption in the body [19]. Several biases can occur in collecting data on energy intake and protein intake, namely, from respondents, interviewers, or nutritional intake data processing programs. Because data collection was based on respondents' memories, there was a possibility of recall bias. Bias from the interviewer can be in the form of an error in interpreting the household size (URT) used by the respondent, which can be in the form of overestimate or underestimate the intake consumed by the respondent and errors in the technique of eliciting answers. Weaknesses in nutritional analysis programs are usually errors in the program's database, where there may be a mismatch between the nutritional content of food ingredients in the program's database and actual reality.

Conclusion

The results of this study indicate that there is no correlation between total protein and energy intake and hemoglobin levels in obese adolescents. From this research, data was obtained in the form of body mass index for obese samples, low levels of total protein and energy intake per day, and low hemoglobin levels in adolescents, which can be used as a basis for providing education for adolescents to improve healthier lifestyles.

Suggestions for further research are to also check the data in the database for measuring food intake.

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